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REVIEW ARTICLE

Plants: An Infinite Source of Molecules Useful for Pharmaceuticals

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Abstract: Since ancient times, plants played a basic role for humans and resulted in a fundamental resource both for surviving in the environment and for life quality improving. Particularly, many plants had specific properties which can be applied for some benefits to human health. Moreover, the large variability of plant species, located in different regions of the planet, has led to the development of distinct cultures and then to the use of plants as pharmaceuticals. In recent times, the use of plants as pharmaceuticals has moved from the historical empirical knowledge and applications to more scientific uses. Presently, a large number of plant-derived pharmaceuticals are used by humans and in view of growing human needs, extensive research activities have started for discovering new plant molecules. It is becoming clear that the wide diversity of natural compounds is a powerful stock for new pharmaceuticals against old and new pathologies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

During time the human's evolution was related to a continuous increasing of technological gains by which humans became able to live in different climates and environments, to get nutrients and foods and to establish life conditions allowing the survival of their progeny. The characteristic human talent for observing, comparing, thinking and, after careful evaluation, exploiting the available natural resources constituted fundamental milestones in the progress of human society. Presently science and technology are playing a fundamental

role in the development of the human society, pushing to new frontiers and carrying out a careful reinvestigation and evaluation of past human activities.

Since ancient times, plants were used to improve human health thanks to their specific properties, resulting in a fundamental resource for both surviving and rising up life quality. Furthermore, due to the large variability of vegetable species located in different regions of the planet, plants have been exploited over the centuries in many different ways, based on the customs and the traditions of the different cultures and ethnicities in the world, such as Chinese, Indians, Sumerians, Assyrians, Egyptians, Jewish, Greeks, Romans and Arabs folkloristic cultures, leading eventually at their modern use as pharmaceuticals.

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In recent times, in advanced Countries the use of plants as pharmaceuticals has moved from an empirical (traditional) knowledge and applications to more scientific uses, based on the isolation and characterization of the plant "active principle", the evaluation of its biological molecular mechanism(s) and the synthesis of the molecule(s) by chemical procedures developed in laboratories; such scientific approach allows a more precise investigations at both research and clinical level, an accurate dose of administration of the drug and a wide diffusion and use of the products.

At present, all over the world, a large number of pharmaceuticals from plants are used by humans and recently, in view of growing human needs and as a consequence of wider marketing perspectives, extensive research activities have started for discovering new plant molecules potentially useful for human health [1-5]. Further, new perspectives are also coming from the use of plant molecules as antibacterial applied in agriculture [6] thus opening possibilities for plant molecules as environmental pharmaceuticals.

2. PLANTS AS USEFUL TOOLS FOR TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

Traditional medicine consisted of different components such as botany, anthropology and Religions and had a crucial role in human history because constituted an application field for plant preparation. During history, the different cultures distributed in different planet regions gained always growing knowledge of plants having pharmaceutical properties: in European Western Countries some people gained even more skills about healing preparations and a new professional role defined "Apothecarys" rise up, and consequently a more scientific branch termed "Pharmacy" started.

The history of Pharmacy was for a long time accomplished with the history of Pharmacognosy, defined as a pharmaceutical discipline in 1815. The term Pharmacognosy means "*the science which studies everything about drugs originating from plants or animals in all aspects [7], except under the physiological effect, to describe them correctly and under a general vision*" [8]. It is a milestone for human health needs and it can be considered as the mother of all present-day pharmaceutical disciplines.

In recent time considerable improvement of knowledge in scientific disciplines such as Biology, Pharmacy, Chemistry and Medicine occurred and nowadays many pharmaceuticals come directly from the lab and result as a products of advanced research activities [9]; in addition, the discovery of new molecules and active principles for new pharmaceuticals are also related to the sciences of ethnobotany - "*the study of the interrelationships of primitive men and plants*" [10] - and ethnopharmacognosy that provide the guide towards different sources and classes of compounds.

The use of plants in traditional medicine systems of many cultures has been widely documented [11] and many different medicines, including important drugs still widely in use today, have been produced during time on the base of the knowledge coming from Ayurvedic, Unani, Chinese, European, African, Central, South and North American cultures [1].

Following is a brief overview of the main cultures which have developed an own traditional medicine over the centuries has been reported.

3. CHINESE TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

It is a very ancient system of medicine, believed to be more than 5000 years old, and is based on two separate theories about the natural laws that govern good health and longevity, namely *yin* and *yang*, and the five elements (*wu xing*) *earth*, *metal*, *water*, *wood* and *fire* related to the main organs of the body.

The Modern Day Encyclopedia of Chinese materia medica published in 1977 is the most complete reference of Chinese herbal prescription and reports about 6000 drugs out of which 4800 are of plant origin. Chinese herbs are usually given in fixed mixtures of up to 20 herbs [12]. Chinese traditional medicine is widely diffused also in Western Countries and in recent times researchers are starting to investigate the effects of such curative preparations to find out the active principles contained inside and their mechanisms of action.

4. AYURVEDIC MEDICINE (INDIAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE)

The term Ayurveda derives from the Sanskrit words "*Ayar*" (Life) and "*Veda*" (Science or Knowledge), is one of the most ancient medicinal

practices and also presently it is widely diffused and applied in India. Ayurvedic medicine is considered as a holistic health approach to the human body and mind. The philosophical principles and the use of herbs as medicinal plants suggested by this approach are contained in thousands of poetic hymns included in a text named Rig Veda, presumably written about 2000 years B.C. Ayurvedic medicine had influence on Greek and Middle Eastern medicinal traditions [13] and it is also popular in Western Countries, while in Russia it was introduced after the Chernobyl disaster [14].

5. ARABIC (UNAMI-TIBB) AND NORTH AFRICAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

The oldest written information in the medicinal Arabic tradition is a clay cuneiform tablets coming from Mesopotamia [8]. The Hammurabi Code (ca. 1700 BC) also reported, in addition to laws, also a list of medicinal herbs. Moreover, Egyptian people wrote their medical and pharmaceutical knowledge on papyrus and in wall-paintings of tombs. The most important of these writings is the medical handbook known as “Ebers Papyrus” (from the name of Georges Ebers who discovered the papyrus in 1872) written around 1550 BC, 9th year of Amenhotep I reign, and containing medicinal knowledge from before 3000 BC.

The Arabs preserved much of the Greco-Roman medicinal knowledge (see below) and improved and expanded it including their own resources. They also contributed to diffuse to the West the Chinese and Indian cultures in the use of herbs. In the 8th century, drug stores were established in Arab regions and the Persian pharmacist (and also physician, philosopher and poet) Avicenna (Abù’Alì al Husayn ibn Sinà) produced the “*Canon medicinae*”, a fundamental treatise of Medicine which included elements of other medicinal cultures and provided information for a distinct system of Islamic healing. Such system is today known as Unani-Tibb [15].

6. EUROPEAN MEDICINE

In the ancient Western world, Greeks made a great contribution to the rational use of herbal drugs and the healing system is said to have originated with Hippocrates (460-377 BC) and Aristotle (384-322 BC). However, the roots of Greek healing culture came from the ancient healing cul-

tures of India (partially through Egyptian healing culture).

Dioscorides, a Greek physician who travelled with Roman armies through the Empire, first introduced the term “botanike” in plant writings. He was the author of the famous book “*De Materia Medica*”, in which 813 medicinal herbs were reported. *De Materia Medica* is one of the oldest European herbal treatise and it was the source of reference in Europe for more than 1000 years. Galen (130-200 AC), a Greek studios in pharmacy and medicine sciences that was active in Rome, published 30 books on these subjects and is still known for his prescriptions and formulas used to prepare drugs, sometimes containing dozens of ingredients (galenicals, term still used today). In the lower Middle Age medicinal plants were cultivated according to a standardized layout in monasteries in Central Europe and the Benedictine abbess Hildegard of Bingen (1098-1179) is still remembered as a famous healer as well as the founder of the scientific natural history in German. In Italy, particular contribution to the development of a healing culture came from the studies of Pietro Hispano (then Pope Johan XXI, 1205-1277) with his book entitled the “*Thesaurus Pauperum*”, from Pier Andrea Mattioli (1501-1577) and his treatise “*Pedanii Dioscoridis Anazarbei De medica materia libri sex*” and from the naturalist Castore Durante (1529-1590) with his book “*Herbario Nuovo*”. In that time plants from Botanical Gardens named “*Giardini dei Semplici*” (“Garden of the Simple”), which were located in proximity or within the hospitals, were used as a single component (“Simple”) or as a component of a complex mixture prepared by the apothecary following the physician request.

Presently, in Europe, herbal medicine is a popular alternative to medicinal products derived from pure synthetic chemicals.

7. AFRICAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

African traditional medicine is probably the oldest of all medicine systems although it remains poorly recorded. Because of the intense process of deforestation a loss of habitats of some medicinal plants is occurring and for this reason, the documentation of medicinal uses of African plants is becoming very urgent. In this view the book enti-

tled "A textbook of medicinal plants from Nigeria" [16] represents an interesting and useful report and contribution.

African traditional medicine involves both the body and mind and is a mix of herbalism and spirituality. The healer typically treats the psychological basis of an illness before the symptoms.

8. CENTRAL AND SOUTH AMERICA

In common with Africa, Central and South American Countries have very rich and diverse healing cultures which are poorly known and have not been properly recorded.

Some new investigations involving the chemistry of ancient hair samples demonstrated the presence of the cocaine metabolite benzoylecgonine (BZE) on Chilean mummies dated 2000 BC to 1500 AC. [17] and traces of nicotine have also been found in hair samples from Nubian burial sites of both children and adults showing that plants containing nicotine may have been used as medical treatments [18]. In addition, the use of a hallucinogenic substances derived from the roasted seeds of the leguminous plant *Anadenanthera peregrina* was suggested by the archaeological evidence in other groups from the region [19].

9. NORTH AMERICA

In the US and Canada, as in many other ancient cultures, the indigenous healer, the Shaman, had a physical and spiritual approach to diseases. Early settlers adopted many of the herbal remedies from native practices; for instance the plant of the genus *Salvia* was used by the Indian tribes of southern California in childbirth and male new-born babies were literally "cooked" in the hot ashes of *Salvia* in order to promote their growth as the strongest and healthiest member of the respective tribes and to preserve them from any kind of respiratory ailments for the whole life [20]. The herbal cures from native practices later formed the basis of the Pharmacopeia of the United States. In recent years, herbs have become very popular in the US and Canada although they are still considered as nutritional supplements rather than medicines. However, it should be noted that since the multicultural content of US populations, in such Country all mentioned healing cultures find the application.

9.1. From Plants Towards Pharmaceuticals

As a consequence of man needs and experimenting, during time plant components have been used as traditional medicines, remedies, potions and oils without any knowledge about the bioactive compounds contained inside [21, 20]. In rich Countries, mainly European Western Countries, the continuous improvement of scientific knowledge occurred during the past centuries allowed to move from plants to pharmaceuticals. The scientific and cultural revolution that started from the development of the lens and the derived new instrumentations, such as the microscope, opened new perspectives in many fields: in particular the cellular components of the human body, animals and insects, peculiarities of plants, algae and fungi consistently contributed for the improvement of the human knowledge and, as a consequence, of the human progress. Following the "lens revolution", as well as the related "Scientific Method" introduced by Galileo Galilei (1564-1642), new technologies for detailed studies of living and not-living matter were developed.

One of the most explicative examples of process for moving from plants towards pharmaceuticals has a documented example in the development of Aspirine, the commercial name of the active principle consisting of acetylsalicylic acid, originally derived from the salix bark. The use of salix bark as a curative plant has ancient origins, indeed as Egyptians used infusions of the salix bark to cure fever a later confirmed by the Greek physician Dioscoride and, many centuries later, also by the Italian naturalist Castore Durante, who mentioned many other curative uses of such plant. The modern history of the development of a pharmaceutical drug from salix started from the second half of XVIII century when the bark extract showed curative properties for malaric fevers. Such observations stimulated research activities in many labs of different Countries, mainly from chemical point of view in order to identify the active principle and its possible production by chemical synthesis: in 1853 the chemist Charles Frédéric Gerhardt produced acetylsalicylic acid for the first time by treating the sodium salicylate with acetyl chloride [22]. In 1897 the Bayer company starts to investigate acetylsalicylic acid as replacement drugs for the salicylate medicines, that were more common at that time but much more irritating. Finally, in

1899 acetylsalicylic pills acid went into industrial production and arrived on the market as pills named "Aspirine" [22-25]. Since that time, many acetylsalicylic derivatives have been obtained, accurately tested and widely used all over the world.

Another example of a plant active principle standardised as pharmaceutical is represented by the Quina tree (*Cinchona* tree) extract, originally used in Peru by natives against malaria fever induced, as then discovered, by four species of the parasite *Plasmodium*, namely *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. ovale*, *P. malariae*. In Europe Quina tree was imported in XVII century and used as powder which was then diffused with the name "Jesuit Powder" in all the world. At the beginning of XIX century, an active principle consisting of an alkaloid named chinine was isolated and chemically characterized, thus opening perspectives for the development of pharmaceuticals [24, 26].

Another important plant molecule, presently very well known and widely used as commercial drugs, is the alkaloid morphine, firstly isolated from *Papaverum sonniferum* L (opium poppy) in 1803 by Friedrich Sertürner and commercialized by Merck in 1827 [27]. As it has the tendency to cause sleep, Sertürner originally called this substance morphium in honor of the Greek God of dreams Morpheus [28, 29]. This molecule acts directly on the Central nervous System (CNS) decreasing the feeling of pain, and it is used as a pain medication in many different cases, including acute and chronic pain [30]. This alkaloid also used to produce other famous pharmaceutical molecules since in the 1870s: for example, crude morphine was converted in diacetylmorphine (heroin) after boiling in acetic anhydride, and such new molecule was found to be readily converted to codeine (painkiller) [31]. From a historical point of view, it has been documented that Sumerians and ancient Greeks used poppy extract for its curative power and tracks of opium used as addictive have been also found in Arabs ancient culture [32].

A very famous and popular pharmaceutical product derived from plants is Taxol, widely used in the treatment of breast cancer and starting from 1992, it has received several FDA approvals for various application [33]. Taxol was isolated from the bark of *Taxus brevifolia* (Pacific Yew) and the first extraction was performed by Monroe Wall and Mansukh Wani at the United States Depart-

ment of Agriculture (USDA) and dates back to 1967 [34]. After that, Taxol has been commercially developed by Bristol-Myers Squibb as "Paclitaxel". The importance of such new drug resulted in a massive increment of the demand and the contemporary low yield of extraction from the bark have lead the pharmaceutical industries to develop methods to synthetically produce "Paclitaxel" [35], despite the high costs and difficulties inherent to the process [36].

Something of similar has occurred for many plants; starting from ancient uses of plants, between XIX and XX centuries their active principles were identified, chemically synthesised and used as pharmaceuticals. It should be noted that in some cases, on the basis of the present level of scientific knowledge, isolated active plant principles found different pharmaceutical uses respect to the traditional, sometimes ancient, use of the plant.

9.2. Plants: An Established Source for Pharmaceuticals

9.2.1. Secondary Metabolites

From ancient times, sugars, proteins and lipids and few other molecules of plant source have been the main components of human diet and needs, and as a consequence some plant species were specifically selected and widely cultured. Nevertheless, the level of study and improvement of plant knowledge still remains relatively low if compared to other fields of human activity: it should be noted that, among hundreds of thousands of plant species present on the planet, only a few played a direct fundamental role in the progress of humanity and our knowledge of plants still remains low and mainly related to those plants having dietary importance or industrial uses. Despite of plants play key roles in the whole planet living system, representing a basic component of the human and animal diet and finding basic application in the industries of clothing, building, furniture, pharmacy and paper, it has been estimated that only about 6% of the plant kingdom has been investigated from a biological point of view and 15% in terms of chemical components. Except for people specifically interested in the plant field and its derivatives, mainly agro-food derivatives, a large part of worldwide human population considers plants as simple and not very important living organisms. More recently scientists enlarged their

investigation to plants not selected as of human interest in the past and presently new plants, in some cases confined to certain regions of the planet, seem to open new perspectives for human needs and applications: many biotechnological investigations are being carried out with the perspectives for using plants as molecule producers of industrial interest (molecular farming), producing biofuel, offering a contribution for future needs of energy and developing biodegradable plastic in order to reduce plastic pollution, a consistent and increasing problem for the present and the future of human society.

Although plants cannot move and have no complex organs as animals, due to their cell structure, consisting in the presence of a cell wall surrounding the cell, specialized organelles such as plastids and a large vacuole in the cytoplasm, as well as to many biochemical and physiological processes similar to animal cells they are classified as eukaryotic organisms. Moreover, plant cells have a very complex cellular metabolism producing, in addition to primary compounds like sugars, proteins, lipids and nucleic acids found in all living organisms, a wide number of different molecules termed as secondary metabolites.

It has been well established that secondary metabolites result as specific components of specialised plant structures and organs [37] and a large literature and many well documented books are now available on a such very interesting topic. Secondary metabolites play different roles within plants such as defence against soil microbes, plant viruses and herbivorous animals, and in the process of reproduction by producing flower pigments (terpenoid carotenes, phenolics and flavonoids), fruits having particular fragrances (terpene and phenolic compounds) for attracting pollinators and involving insects and animals as dispersal agents thereby increasing the possibility to enlarge the number of individuals in the environment. In addition, secondary metabolites may also inhibit the growth of competitor plants and are often involved in key interactions between plants and their abiotic and biotic environments, thus leading to evolutionary associations between particular groups of pests and plants.

Secondary metabolites can be classified on the basis of their chemical structure, composition, solubility in various solvents, or the mechanism by

which they are synthesized. In terms of chemistry many of them have been identified as phenolic and flavonoid compounds (8,000 different kinds of such compounds known) as terpenes and terpenoids (more than 25,000 different compounds) and alkaloids (the estimated number is around 12,000 different types).

As well established and reported also in school texts, the production of secondary metabolites is dependent on complex pathways derived from basic primary metabolites. The first step for secondary metabolite production includes the formation of specific enzymes, which are involved in the transformation of some primary metabolism products into secondary metabolites. In the pathways for secondary metabolite production, processes of molecule oxidation occur. The oxidizing reactions are commonly catalysed by dioxygenases, enzymes which utilize oxygen and α -ketoglutarate; in addition to specific secondary metabolites, CO₂ and succinate are also released. Other typical steps of secondary metabolite biosynthesis require the methylation of potentially reactive carboxylic acid, amino and hydroxyl groups that can spontaneously interact and form products that are undesirable to the plant and then stored within the vacuole.

In many plants, the secondary metabolites content is very low, although rich in a number of compounds. Depending on human needs and in relation to the chemical structure complexity, a large amount of molecules can be further obtained by chemical laboratory processes.

10. THE DISCOVERY OF PLANT ACTIVE MOLECULES

Presently, the evaluation of the potential interest of plants and plant derivatives can be carried out using different approaches. The interest in new plant molecules is dependent on many cross-linked different aspects such as availability of funds supporting the research activity, market interests, industrial research plans, governmental decisions, new pharmaceutical needs and, not of little importance, specific scientific interest of researchers.

The first step of the research, consisting in the selection of plants to be investigated, can depend on different aspects. In some case plants are selected on the basis of their old uses for human needs or as components of traditional medicine

and a precious source of old uses of plants is represented by traditional religious rituals and mortuary ceremonies. Nowadays, because of necessity of new molecules for human needs, they represent a precious source for advanced research. Plants are sometimes selected following both the indications and preliminary studies already reported in old books of Botany and Medicine, thus offering a more scientific starting point for further detailed investigations.

Due to the available facilities allowing to carry out more accurate investigations, a large number of plants can be randomly tested. Depending on plants, the whole plant or specific parts such as roots, leaves, flowers or fruits can be used as starting material to be investigated for evaluating possible biological activities; in order to get molecules from the whole plant or specific parts, a careful evaluation of the research plan (often consisting of an interdisciplinary approach) based on chemical investigations and biological tests is established according to scientific literature.

Chemical investigations are carried out in order to define the chemical structure of plant bioactive molecules. The first step consists in an extraction procedure which allow to collect molecules without affecting their chemical structure. Molecules are then separated by chromatography techniques (thin layer chromatography, column chromatography, high performance liquid chromatography) and their chemical structure is investigated through mass spectrometry and nuclear magnetic resonance methodologies. Sometimes, after the identification of the chemical structure, plant bioactive molecules can be synthesized in the lab, in order to perform more precise experiments for evaluating their biological activity. The evaluation of the biological activity of the identified plant molecules has been then performed by *in vitro* tests carried out on specific cell lines which usually mimic the human pathologies: the choice of the most appropriated cell model is a very important step. The obtained results can potentially lead to develop new molecules with specific activities and applications useful to develop new pharmaceuticals: molecules against cancer or degenerative pathologies, molecules with antimicrobial activities with potential perspectives for new antibiotics, molecules with antiviral activities and related perspectives for new antiviral pharmaceuticals, molecules

with properties of interaction/stimulation the human immunosystem with perspectives for immunomodulating pharmaceuticals, molecules with properties for maintaining the efficiency of the blood system with perspectives for blood system pharmaceuticals, molecules with properties for enabling the mechanism of sperm movement thus contributing for new human contraception pharmaceuticals.

The results of such *in vitro* investigations are also dependent on the accuracy of the screening methods and biological tests specificity and in recent times, thanks to the running scientific improvements, well established screening methods and accurate protocols for biological tests are available [38-40]. As a different research approach, it is also possible to use a *virtual screening* software to test libraries of compounds on panels of targets characterizing different pathologies [41]. Depending on the research aims, molecules showing bioactive properties are further experimented in a preclinical phase using animals as model and if such tests confirm the *in vitro* or the *virtual screening* results without effect on the animal models, further human experimentation can start. The human experimental protocol(s) must be carried out and evaluated following precise guidelines established at the international level. It consists of different steps (phases) of investigation during which accurate biochemical studies are carried out to establish the drug human target(s) and the molecular mechanism(s) of action; in addition, toxicological investigations are carried out to evaluate their dose and efficiency, the interaction with the human cell and body defence systems, human tolerance and the degree of potential side-effects. Such studies are carried out on a large group of humans consisting of children, women and men from different Countries. At the end of the whole process (some years required), from the selection of plants to the pharmaceutical product, it has been established that only one molecule among about 3000 good candidate bioactive molecules can result as a potential pharmaceutical.

Depending on the continuous growth of the world human population and the improvement of life quality, the demand for new pharmaceuticals increased a lot and as a consequence an increase in pharmaceutical research activity occurred. Presently Pharmaceutical Industries and Drug Discov-

ery Companies play an active role in terms of research and marketing of pharmaceutical products and related business.

CONCLUSION

Plants and all the other living organisms can be viewed as a combination of molecules that can interfere with other organisms and living systems and, if we consider the number of plants living in the world as a complex combination of many different chemical compounds, we can realize that an infinite source of molecules having pharmaceutical properties is available. In the last years, researches on natural substances increased a lot, involving especially plants coming from different planet regions, and leading to the development of a wide range of new pharmaceuticals against old and new pathologies. Looking at such present landscape, plants along with all the other sources of natural products will become a really important element for the future of the human, providing the starting material to develop products needed for the pharmaceuticals, the nutritional needs, as well as the raw materials which allow to carry on a sustainable work for many different industries.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Gurib-Fakim A. Medicinal plants: Traditions of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow. *Mol Aspects Med* 2006; 27: 1-93.
- [2] Mishra BB, Tiwari VK. Natural products: An evolving role in future drug discovery. *Eur J Med Chem* 2011; 46(10): 4769-807.
- [3] Dias DA, Urban S, Roessner U. A historical overview of natural products in drug discovery. *Metabolites* 2012; 2: 303-36.
- [4] Newman DJ, Cragg GM. Natural products as sources of new drugs from 1981 to 2014. *J Nat Prod* 2016; 79: 629-61.
- [5] Bernardini S, Tiezzi A, Laghezza-Masci V, Ovidi E. Plants and other organisms as sources of useful molecules for human health. 2017 In Press.
- [6] Quattrucci A, Ovidi E, Tiezzi A, Vinciguerra V, Bal-estra GM. Biological control of tomato bacterial speck using *Punica granatum* fruit peel extract. *Crop Protect* 2013; 46: 18-22.
- [7] Kinghorn AD. Pharmacognosy in the 21st century. *J Pharm Pharmacol* 2011; 53: 135-48.
- [8] Heinrich M, Barnes J, Gibbons S, Williamson EM. *Fundamentals of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. Churchill Livingstone, 2004, Elsevier Science Ltd., UK.
- [9] DeCorte BL. Underexplored opportunities for natural products in drug discovery. *J Med Chem* 2016; 59: 9295-304.
- [10] Jones V. The nature and scope of ethnobotany. *Chronica Botanica* 1941; 6: 219-21.
- [11] Samuelsson G. *Drugs of Natural Origin: A textbook of pharmacognosy*. 5th Swedish Pharm Press, 2004, Stockholm.
- [12] Chang HM, But PPH. *Pharmacology and Applications of Chinese Materia Medica*. World Sci. Publ., Singapore, Chadwick D.J. and Marsh J. (Eds.), *Ethnobotany and the Search for New Drugs*. Ciba Found. 1986.
- [13] Samy RP, Pushparaj PN, Gopalakrishnakone P. A compilation of bioactive compounds from Ayurveda. *Bioinformation* 2008; 3(3): 100-10.
- [14] Ragozin BV. The history of the development of Ayurvedic medicine in Russia. *Anc Sci Life* 2010; 35(3): 143-9.
- [15] Jabin F. A guiding tool in Unani Tibb for maintenance and preservation of health: A review study. *Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med* 2011; 8(5): 140-3.
- [16] Odugbemi T. *A textbook of medicinal plants from Nigeria*. University of Lagos Press, Akoka, Yaba-Lagos, Nigeria, 2008. ISBN: 978-978-48712-9-7.
- [17] Baez H, Castro MM, Benavente MA, Kintz P, Cirimele V, Camargo C, Thoma C. Drugs in prehistory: Chemical analysis of ancient human hair. *Sci Inter* 2000; 108: 173-9.
- [18] Balabanova S, Rosing FW, Teschler-Nicola M, Strouhal E, Buhler G, Michael C, Rosenthal J. Was nicotine used as a stimulant already in the VI century A.D. from the Christian Sayala population? *J Paleopathol* 1996; 8: 43-50.
- [19] McKenna T. *El Manjar de los Dioses*. Ed. Paidós, Barcelona, Spain, 1993.
- [20] Hicks S. *Desert plants and people*. 1st ed., San Antonio (TX): Naylor Co, 2014.
- [21] Kinghorn AD, Pan L, Fletcher JN, Chai H. The relevance of higher plants in lead compound discovery programs. *J Nat Prod* 2011; 74: 1539-55.
- [22] Diarmuid J. *Aspirin the remarkable story of a wonder drug*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2008.
- [23] Vane JR, Botting RM. *The history of aspirin*. *Aspirin Other Salicylates* 1992; 3-16.
- [24] Felisati D. Quinine and aspirin: Two parallel stories with many touching points. *Acta otorhinolaryng Italica* 2000; 20: 290-3.
- [25] Porojic D. A historical overview of the discovery of aspirin with some new aspects on its development. *Arhiv za Farmaciju* 2003; 53: 51-70.

- [26] Eiden F. An excursion into the past: Quinine and other quina alkaloids. 3. The path to total synthesis of quinoline-quina alkaloids in the development of more effective malaria drugs before research on the indole-quina alkaloids. *Pharmazie in unserer Zeit* 1999; 28: 74-86.
- [27] Courtwright DT. *Forces of habit drugs and the making of the modern world* (1 ed.). Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press. pp. 36-37, 2009.
- [28] Mosher CJ. *Drugs and Drug Policy: The Control of Consciousness Alteration*. SAGE Publications, 2013,123
- [29] Fisher GL. *Encyclopedia of substance abuse prevention, treatment, & recovery*. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2009, 564.
- [30] Osikowicz M, Mika J, Makuch W, Przewlocka B. Glutamate receptor ligands attenuate allodynia and hyperalgesia and potentiate morphine effects in a mouse model of neuropathic pain. *Pain* 2008; 139(1): 117-26.
- [31] Dias DA, Urban S, Roessner U. A historical overview of natural products in drug discovery. *Metabolites* 2012; 2: 303-36.
- [32] Der Marderosian A, Beutler JA. *The review of natural products*. 3rd ed. St. Louis (MO): Facts and Comparisons, 2002.
- [33] Cseke LJ, Kirakosyan A, Kaufmann PB, Warber SL, Duke JA, Briemann HL. *Natural products from plants*. 2nd ed. Boca Raton (FL): CRC, Taylor and Francis, 2006.
- [34] Cragg GM. Paclitaxel (Taxol): A success story with valuable lessons for natural product drug discovery and development. *Med Res Rev* 1998; 18: 315-31.
- [35] Dewick PM. *Medicinal natural products: A biosynthetic approach*. 3rd ed. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [36] Nicolaou KC, Yang Z, Liu JJ, *et al.* Total synthesis of taxol. *Nature* 1994; 367: 630-4.
- [37] Bell EA. Secondary plant products. In "Encyclop. Plant Physiology Vol. 8" B. V. Charlwood (Eds), Berlin-Heidelberg-New York: Springer Verlag, 1980
- [38] Parasuraman S. Toxicological screening. *J Pharmacol Pharmacother* 2011; 2(2): 74-9.
- [39] Jones WP, Kinghorn AD. Extraction of plant secondary metabolites. *Methods Mol Biol* 2012; 864: 341-66.
- [40] Bucar F, Wube A, Schmid M. Natural product isolation - how to get from biological material to pure compounds. *Nat Prod Rep* 2013; 30: 525-45.
- [41] Lauro G, Masullo M, Piacente S, Riccio R, Bifulco C. Inverse virtual screening allows the discovery of the biological activity of natural compounds. *Bioorg Med Chem* 2012; 20: 3596-602.